

Use of Potassium Bromate : Bromination of Benzoic Acid

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Production of *m*-bromobenzoic acid by bromination of benzoic acid using potassium bromate has been studied under different experimental conditions.

THE oxidation of benzaldehyde by potassium bromate in (4*N*) sulphuric acid produced a mixture of benzoic and *m*-bromobenzoic acids¹. The formation of the latter may involve the bromination of benzaldehyde prior to oxidation or the reverse may be the reaction but it appeared to be a unique and extraordinary use of potassium bromate for the smooth introduction of bromine in aromatic nucleus heretofore unknown to us. This reaction has so much potentiality that a thorough study has been made using benzoic acid as the pilot compound to establish the optimum conditions for bromination followed by its application for the preparation of a host of bromoaromatic compounds. It had been observed¹ that when potassium bromate was strongly heated in (4*N*) sulphuric acid, bromine and oxygen were liberated. It had been also found that neither the elemental nor the nascent bromine, liberated from a mixture of potassium bromide and potassium bromate with dilute sulphuric acid, could induce bromination in benzoic acid under the experimental conditions. When either (0.5*N*) sulphuric acid or glacial acetic acid was used with potassium bromate no bromination was observed but moderately concentrated (4-8*N*) sulphuric acid and dropwise addition of potassium bromate solution under refluxing condition were effective in brominating to the extent of 87% producing *m*-bromobenzoic acid. The yield of the desired product was reduced when either stronger sulphuric acid (12*N*) was used or all portion of the required potassium bromate was added at the very beginning of the reaction. It was also noted that approximately one mole of benzoic acid required one mole of potassium bromate for this reaction. The isolation of 3, 4-dibromobenzoic acid from a large amount of bromination product of benzoic acid, though in extremely poor yield, was very suggestive of the brominating action of potassium bromate in the substituted aromatic acids which has been studied and will be communicated in future.

Experimental

A. R. acetic acid was heated under reflux with excess of potassium dichromate for six hours and distilled just before use. Pure potassium bromate, sulphuric acid and distilled water were used whenever needed.

1.(a) Bromination of Benzoic Acid with Potassium Bromate in (4-8*N*) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzoic acid (6.1g ; 0.05 *M*) and sulphuric acid (8*N* ; 125 ml) was heated under reflux to dissolve benzoic acid and a solution of potassium bromate [prepared by dissolving 25.0g of potassium bromate in 250 ml of distilled water] was added dropwise from the separating funnel in course of thirty minutes. The refluxing was continued for another one hour. Flaky colourless crystals began to separate when the reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto iced-water followed by extraction with chloroform. The organic layer was washed with water and treated with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The aqueous alkaline extract was acidified (congo red) with (4*N*) sulphuric acid when colourless acidic material separated. This was extracted with ether (3×100 ml), washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed from a steam bath to furnish a residue (9.5 g), m.p. 134°. The increase in weight indicated 87% yield of the desired product. The crude acid (9.5 g) was esterified with dry ethanol (50 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 ml) by heating under reflux for twelve hours and working up the product in the usual way. The desired compound was obtained as a sweet smelling liquid (8.0 g), b.p. 135-37°/12 mm. The N.M.R. data of the middle fraction of the redistilled material, b.p. 107-108°/10 mm, gave the following signals characterising ethyl 3-bromobenzoate, δ (CCl₄),

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1.40 (t, -CH₃ in carbethoxy-), 4.25 (q, -CH₂-in carbethoxy-), 7.22, 7.50, 7.80 and 8.02 (4H, aromatic).

The aforementioned ester (2.0g), b.p. 135-37/12 mm, was hydrolysed by heating under reflux with a mixture of ethanol (20.0 ml), potassium hydroxide (2.0 g) and few drops of water for two hours. Excess of alcohol was removed and the reaction mixture was dissolved in minimum quantity of distilled water and extracted with ether. The alkaline layer was acidified with (4*N*) sulphuric acid when colourless solid separated which was extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml), washed with distilled-water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent from steambath, a residue (1.9 g), m.p. 141-42°, was obtained which responded strongly to Beilstein test for halogen. On two crystallisations from a mixture of petroleum ether (60-80°) and benzene (1:1), it furnished colourless crystals (1.5 g), m.p. 155°, m.m.p. with authentic *m*-bromobenzoic acid² remained undepressed; the neutral equivalent was 198 ± 5. The I.R. spectra of this sample and authentic *m*-bromobenzoic acid, [ν_{Nujol} 1680, 1590, 1560, 1455, 1440, 998, 939, 900, 831, 816, 745, 700, 668 and 548 cm⁻¹] were identical in all respects. The N.M.R. data also support the identity of 3-bromobenzoic acid, δ (CDCl₃), 7.38, 7.62, 7.95 and 8.20 (4H, aromatic; and carboxy-proton unobserved).

(b) When a mixture of benzoic acid (10.0 g), potassium bromate (20.0 g) and sulphuric acid (4*N*, 100 ml) was heated under reflux for six hours and the reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way, a solid residue was obtained. This was esterified and distilled, b.p. 135-142°/12 mm, to yield a colourless ester (11.7 g, 64%). On hydrolysis this ester furnished *m*-bromobenzoic acid, m.p. 155°, in excellent yield.

2. Attempted Bromination of Benzoic Acid with Elemental Bromine :

A mixture of benzoic acid (5.0 g), sulphuric acid (4*N*; 25.0 ml) and bromine (1.5 ml) was heated under reflux for six hours. The unreacted bromine was decomposed with formic acid and worked up to furnish a residue (5.2 g), m.p. 120°, which on recrystallisation from hot water furnished pure benzoic acid, m.p. and m.m.p. 122°.

3. Attempted Bromination of Benzoic Acid with a Mixture of Potassium Bromate and Potassium Bromide :

A mixture of benzoic acid (12.0 g) and sulphuric acid (4*N*; 100 ml) was heated under reflux with dropwise addition of a mixture of potassium bromide (20.0 g) and potassium bromate (6.0 g), dissolved in water (70.0 ml). After five hours the reaction mixture was cooled and formic acid was added to decompose bromine and worked up to furnish a residue which was esterified and distilled under reduced pressure to

furnish a colourless oil (10.1 g), b.p. 135-145°/water aspirator, which on alkaline hydrolysis furnished pure benzoic acid in excellent yield.

4. Attempted Bromination of Benzoic Acid with Potassium Bromate in (0.5*N*) Sulphuric Acid or Glacial Acetic Acid :

A mixture of benzoic acid (5.0 g), potassium bromate (10.0 g) and dilute sulphuric acid (0.5*N*; 400 ml) was heated under reflux for three and a half hours. The reaction mixture was worked up but only pure benzoic acid was recovered unchanged. The above reaction was repeated with glacial acetic acid (50 ml) but the benzoic acid remained unreacted under the experimental conditions.

5. Bromination of Benzoic Acid with Potassium Bromate in (12*N*) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzoic acid (10.0 g), sulphuric acid (12*N*; 100 ml) and potassium bromate (20.0 g) was heated under reflux for two hours. The reaction mixture was worked up to furnish a residue (13.1 g), m.p. 101-113°, which responded strongly to Beilstein test for halogen. The increase in weight of the product indicated that it contained 47% *m*-bromobenzoic acid.

6. Bromination of Benzoic Acid with Varying Amount of Potassium Bromate :

To a mixture of benzoic acid (25.0 g; 0.2 *M*) and sulphuric acid (4-8*N*; 100 ml/165 ml/250 ml) in separate experiments, potassium bromate solution [8.4 g, 0.05 *M*, in 100 ml; 16.7 g, 0.1 *M* in 165 ml and 25.1 g, 0.15 *M*, in 250 ml of water respectively] was added dropwise and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for one and a half-hours in each case. The reaction mixture was cooled and worked up to furnish *m*-bromobenzoic acid in almost quantitative yield in each case.

7. Isolation of 3,4-dibromobenzoic Acid from the Product of Bromination of Benzoic Acid :

The mixture of acidic material (27.0 g, obtained from several bromination experiments) was esterified in the usual way to furnish a crude ester (32.0 g) which furnished fraction-(a) 14.7 g, b.p. 80-85°/10 mm, and (b) 6.0 g, b.p. 109-110°/10 mm. A residue (2.9 g) was obtained which on alkaline hydrolysis furnished an acid which on repeated crystallisations from dilute ethanol furnished a colourless material (65 mg), m.p. 234°, which was identified to be 3,4-dibromobenzoic acid³. The neutral equivalent of this compound was found to be 275 ± 5. Mass spectrum indicated following significant fragments: M⁺ (278, 280, 282), M-OH (261, 263, 265) and M-CO₂H (233, 235, 237), as strong peaks. Calculated for C₇H₄Br₂O₂, C, 30.00%; H, 1.43%. Found C, 30.16%; H, 1.82%. Ethyl ester of the compound was prepared and the following N.M.R.

peaks were observed, δ (CCl_4), 1.40 (t , $-\text{CH}_3$), 4.27 (q , $-\text{CH}_2-$) 7.38, 7.68 and 7.80 (3H, aromatic).

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